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Interlingual Phraseological Equivalents and Analogies

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***Abstract:** This article explores interlingual phraseological equivalents and analogies in English, Russian and Uzbek, analyzing their meaning, structure, and cultural significance. Phraseological equivalents maintain both conceptual and figurative correspondence between languages, while analogies differ in imagery but convey the same meaning. The study examines various examples, demonstrating how phraseological units evolve through linguistic and extralinguistic factors, including cultural and historical influences.*

***Key words:** Interlingual phraseological equivalents, phraseological analogies, linguistic transfer, cross-cultural communication, phraseology, metaphorical thinking, translation studies.*

Introduction

Phraseological units are essential to language because they express historical evolution, culture, and national identity. The study of interlingual phraseological parallels and equivalents is crucial for linguistic research, successful cross-cultural communication, and correct translation in multilingual communication.

Phraseological equivalents are phraseological units that have the same expressive value and meaning in several languages, frequently maintaining the conceptual and figurative foundation. Phraseological analogues, on the other hand, have different imagery and structural compositions yet communicate the same idea. The comparison of phraseological units in English and Uzbek highlights the similarities and differences in linguistic thinking, cultural symbolism, and metaphorical representation.

This article examines the nature of interlingual phraseological equivalence and analogy, focusing on how English and Uzbek phraseological units correspond in meaning, usage, and cultural significance. By analyzing examples from both languages, the study provides insights into the mechanisms of phraseological transfer and adaptation in translation and intercultural discourse.

Methods

To examine the phraseological repertoire of English, Russian, and Uzbek, a shared notion of interlingual phraseological unity must be established. According to V. G. Gak, equivalents are "fixed, equal-meaning correspondences that, most of the time, do not depend on context." When a polysemantic phraseological unit's equivalent covers just one of its meanings, it is said to be partial; when it transmits all of its meanings, it is said to be complete.

Ya. I. Retzker, in the introductory article to the *Italian-Russian Phraseological Dictionary*, offers the following definition of an absolute equivalent: "An absolute equivalent in the Russian language must fully convey not only the semantic meaning but also the expressive-evaluative and functional-stylistic characteristics of the Italian phraseological unit." Furthermore, he states that a simple equivalent of an Italian phraseological unit "can be either a Russian word, a non-figurative phraseological unit, or a figurative phraseological unit in Russian."

It is assumed that a single word can serve as an equivalent for a foreign phraseological unit, then this is no longer a case of phraseological equivalence but rather a matter of more or less adequate transmission of the content of a single phraseological unit from one language to another. Moreover, the translation of a foreign phraseological unit, even if it is identical to it in both semantic and stylistic terms, can only be considered a phraseological equivalent if it exists as a phraseological unit in the Russian language.

According to A. V. Kunin, an equivalent is "an adequate phraseological expression in the Russian language that corresponds to the English one both in meaning and in its figurative basis."

In contrast, V. G. Gak argues that "even absolute equivalents can be created on a completely different figurative basis than the Russian phraseological unit, while maintaining the same expressive effect." A. V. Kunin refers to such phraseological units as "analogues."

According to Yu. P. Solodub, "phraseological correspondences" are primarily interlingual phraseological equivalents that have emerged not through borrowing but based on figurative-associative processes and the logical thinking of different nations.

E. M. Solodukho refers to this type as "interlingual phraseological parallelism."

Results and Discussions

When selecting terms for units of interlingual phraseological commonality, one should primarily rely on the fundamental lexical meaning of each term. Thus, as a neutral, non-specialized term to denote a unit of interlingual phraseological commonality that conveys, to a greater or lesser extent, the content, form, and stylistic characteristics of phraseological units in different languages, it is advisable, in our opinion, to use the term "interlingual phraseological equivalent."

The choice of this term is also determined by its functional characteristic: in linguistics, equivalence refers to "a relationship between linguistic units in which they share a common property, allowing them to perform the same function."

Within the framework of interlingual phraseological equivalents, we distinguish between interlingual phraseological correspondences and interlingual phraseological analogies.

In our opinion, **interlingual phraseological correspondences** include phraseological units that share a common meaning, have similar **figurative structures**, serve **functional-stylistic purposes**, and are **lexically equivalent**.

An example of this is:

- Russian: *За двумя зайцами погонишься, ни одного не поймаешь.*
- English: *If you run after two hares, you will catch neither.*
- Uzbek: *Ikki quyonning orqasidan yugursang , bittasini ham tutolmaysan*

For example, the Russian phraseological unit "последнее слово" (*poslednee slovo*) is not only identical to the English "last word" but also covers all three meanings of its correlate:

1. The decisive word (final decision or authority);
2. The last extreme price (final offer in negotiations);
3. The latest achievement (in science, technology, or progress).

Interlingual phraseological equivalents are identical or correspond in terms of functional-stylistic characteristics (and possibly in structural-grammatical form); however, they differ in lexical composition and, consequently, in imagery. Such equivalents are referred to as interlingual phraseological analogies.

For example:

- English: *All good things must come to an end* (Am.), *Every day is not a holiday* (Am.), *Every day is not Sunday* (Br.), *Good things do not last forever* (Br.)
- Russian: *He все кому масленица* (*Not every day is Pancake Week for the cat*).
- Uzbek: *Har kuni yeganing yog'li palov emas* (*Not every day is an oily pilaf*).
- English: *To cry over spilt milk* (*What falls off the cart is gone—literally: What leaves the hand does not return*).
- Russian: *Что с воза упало, то пропало* (*What has fallen off the cart is lost*).
- English: *Scratch my back and I'll scratch yours*.
- Russian: *Рука руку моет* (*One hand washes the other*).
- Uzbek: *Сиздан угина, биздан бугина* (*A little from you, a little from us*).

In all three examples of English-Russian-Uzbek phraseological analogies, there is identity in the first two parameters (meaning and function) but no correspondence in the third main parameter (lexical composition and imagery). Regarding the fourth, additional parameter: In the first example, the phraseological correlates do not correspond at all. In the second example, there is partial correspondence. In the third example, there is full correspondence.

Conclusion

Interlingual phraseological correspondences typically arise due to linguistic factors, such as mutual phraseological borrowings between the compared languages or shared borrowings from common sources. Therefore, these correspondences exhibit regularity and systematicity. In contrast, the emergence of interlingual phraseological coincidences is determined by extralinguistic factors. As a result, they contain an element of chance. The concept of "coincidence" is narrower than that of "correspondence." An interlingual phraseological coincidence is a type of interlingual phraseological correspondence that has emerged independently in each of the compared languages due to shared

cultural influences, logical thinking, and figurative-associative thought processes of the peoples who speak these languages.

References:

1. Кунин А.В. Курс фразеологии современного английского языка. – Дубна: Феникс+, 2005.
2. Кунин А.В. Фразеология современного английского языка. – М.: Международные отношения, 1972.
3. Fedulenkova T. A new approach to the clipping of communicative phraseological units. In: Ranam: European Society for the Study of English: ESSE 6 – Strasbourg 2002 / Ed. P. Frath & M. Rissanen. – Strasbourg: Université Marc Bloch, 2003. – Vol. 36. – Pp. 11-22.
4. Gavrin S.G. Frazeologiya sovremennogo russkogo yazyka. – Perm, 1974.
5. Mukaramxodjayeva T.Y. “Semantic relationships of phraseological units in English: polysemy and homonymy” So’z san’ati xalqaro jurnali, 7 jild 2 son, Toshkent, 2024
6. Mukaramxodjayeva T.Y. “Interactive methods of teaching language” Международный научный журнал № 8(100), часть 3 «Научный импульс» Март, 2023.
7. Mukaramxodjayeva T.Y., Furqatova M. “O‘zbek va ingliz tilidagi maqollarning o‘xshash va farqli jihatlari” Education and research in the era of digital.,Xalqaro ilmiy anjuman vol1. N1., mart 2025
8. Mukaramxodjayeva T.Y. “Ingliz va o‘zbek tilidagi so‘zlashuv frazeologizmlarining lingvomadaniy xususiyatlari”//Yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o‘rni va rivojlanish omillari Respublika ilmiy anjumani, Vol. 40 No. 1 (2025)
9. Ibayev A.J. Comparative analysis of the derivation of simple sentences in English and Uzbek// International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET) ISSN: 2321-9653; Volume 10 Issue IV Apr 2022. – P. 2146-2150. (SJ Impact Factor: 7.538).
10. Absamadova M.I. Exploring the utility of diplomatic terminology in international relations // Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education. – AQSH, 2024. Volume 2, Issue 5. – P. 630-633 (ISSN: 2994-9521; Impact Factor: 10.37).
11. Absamadova M.I. Activity-oriented approaches in teaching translation methodology // Xorazm Ma’mun akademiyasi axborotnomasi. – Urganch: Xorazm Ma’mun akademiyasi, 2022. № 4/1. – B. 201-205 (10.00.00; №21).